

METHODS OF TRANSLATING BIOLOGICAL TERMS FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK

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Annotation: *This article explores the main methods of translating biological terms from English into Uzbek. It emphasizes the importance of accuracy in scientific translation, particularly in conveying specialized meanings of terms that often lack direct equivalents. The study discusses six commonly used strategies: searching for equivalents, using analogues, calquing, transliteration and transcription, functional sense translation, and descriptive translation with translator’s comments. Examples are provided to illustrate how each method works in practice. The paper concludes that the most effective translation requires a combination of methods, ensuring both linguistic accuracy and contextual appropriateness.*

Keywords: *Translation, biological terms, English, Uzbek, equivalents, analogues, calquing, transliteration, transcription, functional sense, descriptive translation.*

Terms are not just simple words. They have special and complex meanings. Usage of terms is what puts scientific translation apart from other types of translation. Scientific translation is mainly about translating terms in the fields of science and technology of all kinds, such as biology, medicine, physics, chemistry, mathematics, computer sciences...etc. from one language into another.

From Newmark’s standpoint, “the distinction between scientific translation and the other type of translation resides in scientific terms in the texts” [1, p. 151]. The authors’ aesthetic intention is the focus of literary translation whereas the precision of scientific terms contributes to scientific translation accuracy and effectiveness. “Translating terms can be a challenge for translators once even certain bilingual dictionaries of a science fail to distinguish the academic meaning of a term from its common meaning” [2, p. 572].

Since terms are an inevitable part of each scientific text, it is very important to transfer them from source language into target language as properly as possible. There are several techniques to translate scientific terms. Below we will discuss 6 most frequently used methods of term translation in terms of biological terms based on the study by Polyakova [3, pp. 2-3]. They are:

- search for an equivalent.

- use of analogues.
- calquing.
- transliteration/transcription.
- functional sense.
- descriptive translation and translator’s comments.

Below we discuss these translation methods with the examples of translating English biological terms into Uzbek language.

1. The search for an equivalent in the target language, for example, a word that is fully equivalent to its counterpart in the original language. The equivalent should be as short as possible and convey the full volume of the original term meaning. The following terms can serve as examples: cell (hujayra), muscle (mushak), vertebrate (umurtqali), lung (o’pka), etc.

2. The translation with the help of an analogue is used when an original word has several correspondent equivalents in the target language. It is the most widely used translation method, as the practical mass of words is polysemic. For example, germ (spermatozoid, mikrob, embrion (in biology), urug’don, tuguncha (in botany), fungus (zamburug’, po’panak, mog’or), etc.

3. Calquing is the reproduction of a combinational composition of a word or phrase, when the components of a word or a phrase are translated by the relevant elements of the target language. As a translation method calquing served as a basis for many borrowings in the process of intercommunication in cases, when the transliteration was unacceptable for some aesthetic, semantic or other reasons. The essence of calquing is making a new word or an idiom in the target language, which replicates the structure of the original lexical unit: spinal canal (umurtqa kanali), lymph cell (limfa hujayrasi), aortic arch (aorta yoyi), etc.

4. Transliteration/transcription. The transcription is a formal phoneme by phoneme reproduction of an original lexical unit with the help of the target language phonemes, phonetic imitation of the original word. For instance, photosynthesis (fotosintez), metabolism (metabolizm), etc. The other method is transliteration, i.e., formal letter by letter reproduction of the original lexical unit with the help of the target language alphabet, a letter imitation of an original form of a word. For example, molecule (molekula), hybrid (gibrid), ant etc. In this case, the original word in the translated text is presented in the form adapted to the pronunciation features of the target language. These types of translation are mainly used in the translation of proper nouns and names. Besides, the method combining transliteration and transcription is most used in practice.

5. Functional sense. Sometimes the term that has no equivalent or an analogue in the target language, that would convey its meaning sufficiently, is translated with

the help of the words, reflecting its functional sense. For instance, the word “bulb” in the technical texts will be translated as a “lampa”, in astronomy or physics “yoritgich”, and differently in biology: bulb of aorta – aorta piyozchasi; bulb of eye – ko’z soqqasi; spinal bulb – uzunchoq miya according to its functional sense.

6.Descriptive translation and translator’s comments. The descriptive translation, as a rule, is used in parallel with the transcription and is applied when translating terms, culturonims, unique objects, etc., having no lexical equivalents in the target language. The word meaning is presented by means of a common explanation, made as short as possible. If the description as a translation method usually accompanies the word, presented in a simple form, or even is used instead of the word, the translator’s comments are given beyond the text, being mentioned either in the footnotes at the same page or into the endnotes of the text. The comments as a translation method suggests a more detailed (in comparison with the description) explanation of what the original word means in a wide context of that language.

It is necessary to remember that a term is usually translated by a corresponding term in the target language. Such ways of translation as analogues, using synonyms and descriptive translation are used only when there are no equivalent terms for translation.

Concluding all above discussed issues, we can say that using only one method during translation is not a good way. Translators should combine and use them interchangeably during translation. Combination of all above discussed techniques is very important and helpful for good translation.

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